

Variation in tribo-mechanical properties of additive free SiAlON polytypoids densified under different SPS process temperature

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Abstract

The present work reports variations in tribomechanical properties of additive free SiAlON polytypoids as a function of spark plasma sintering temperature. While, at low sintering temperature (1600°C), the specimen was ~82% dense consisting of inadequately grown grains, sintering at 1900°C resulted in >98% dense polytypoid having fibre-like morphology. Irrespective of indentation load used, the 1900°C dense polytypoid offered ~4.5 times higher HV values over the 1600°C sintered specimen. The dense polytypoids offered HV as high as ~21 and ~16 GPa at 0.2 and 2 kgf, respectively. K_{IC} of the dense polytypoids under 10 kgf was found to be ~5.45 MPa-m^{0.5} that indicated self-reinforcing effect offered by the needle shaped grains formed in the polytypoids. Unlubricated linear scratch tests revealed significant improvement in wear resistance at increased sintering temperature. Under 20N, wear rate and COF were found to be ~9.58 x 10⁻⁴ mm³/N-m and ~0.35, respectively, for the 1900°C sintered specimen.

Key words: SiAlON polytype; SPS, Tribo-mechanical properties